

Young people's attitudes to condom use in the UK

Condom use amongst young people is declining globally. A World Health Organisation report found that condom use across Canada, Central Asia and Europe declined among sexually active fifteen year olds by 9% for males and 6% for females between 2014 and 2022. Boys in Scotland, United Kingdom (UK), were the least likely to have used a condom at last sexual intercourse compared to boys in any other country in the report (52% did not use a condom).¹ The reduced rate of condom use increases the risk of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) which can cause serious health consequences.² Reduction in condom use can also increase unplanned pregnancies and an increased risk of pregnancy complications due to STI prevalence.³

This review was commissioned by the Department of Health and Social Care to identify factors that influence condom use amongst young people (aged 15-24) in the UK to inform multiple policy areas.

This review included 25 qualitative studies. The following four themes highlighted factors that influence condom use amongst young people in the UK:

- **Social and community norms:** Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour, with different standards of acceptable behaviour for women and people from certain ethnic minority and religious backgrounds compared to men. Young people generally did not want to talk to their parents about sex or condom use, with the media and peers influencing their knowledge and attitudes towards condoms and perception of risks associated with condom non-use.
- **Institutional factors** highlighted the need for confidential, non-judgmental sexual health care provision and inadequate school education, which emphasised risk reduction through abstinence, overlooking content on STIs, and the need for practical sessions on negotiating condom use.
- **Interpersonal factors** between people in a sexual relationship, with heteronormative power imbalances, difficulties in talking about condom use and trust & familiarity in long-term relationships associated with not using condoms.
- **Intrapersonal factors** including a) psychological characteristics, such as self-esteem and self-efficacy, b) behavioural capability, knowledge & skills relating to condom use, c) attitudes & outcome expectancies, and d) decision-making effort "in the moment" as influenced by alcohol/drug use and condom availability.

Whilst the number of new STI diagnoses in young people reduced by 18.5% in 2024, compared to 2023, young people aged 15-24 continue to experience a high rate of STI diagnoses in the UK.⁽²⁾

Final report

NIHR National Institute for Health and Care Research

How did we do this review?

Finding evidence: We searched databases & websites, conducted citation chasing and asked review interest holders for recommendations of known studies.

Eligibility criteria: UK interview or survey-based studies asking young people, aged 15-24 years, about their experiences relating to the use/non-use of condoms. Studies were published in English from 2014 onwards.

Study selection, data extraction and quality appraisal: Study selection was completed independently by two reviewers. Data extraction & critical appraisal of included studies were carried out by one reviewer & checked by a second.

Synthesis: We brought together findings from included studies using a framework based on theory from a similar systematic review.⁽⁴⁾

Research questions

1. What factors influence condom use among young people within the UK?
2. How do these factors vary for different groups of young people including those associated with health inequities?

What did we find?

A total of 25 studies reported across 29 articles.

Location:

- 16 studies in England.
- 4 studies in Scotland.
- 4 studies across the UK.
- 1 study did not report the specific UK location.

Setting:

- 11 studies set in urban area.
- 2 studies set in rural area.
- 4 studies set across the UK.
- 1 study did not report the specific UK setting.

Study quality

- The median quality appraisal score was 10 out of 14 items (71%).
- 10 studies scored between four to nine.

We identified four themes:

Theme 1: Social and community norms (20 studies)

Disapproval and a lack of understanding of sexual behaviour in the wider society can lead to young people disengaging with sexual health services (including schemes for accessing condoms) and lack of understanding about sexual health in communities where sexual health is not openly discussed.

Gender norms may impact young people's condom use. For example, women who obtain condoms are seen as promiscuous, while men who use condoms, are perceived as demonstrating 'prowess'.

Peer-influence amongst some male groups (including those who are socially excluded) can lead to not using condoms to affirm gender identity within their social group. A desire to hide sexual activity from family can also lead to sex in spaces with limited accessibility to condoms (e.g. outside).

The media was seen to reinforce derogatory attitudes towards women, and within pornography, condomless sex is seen as the norm.

Theme 2: Institutional factors (19 studies)

Young people need non judgemental supportive sexual health services and tailored information, particularly for young women, LGBTQ+ and neuro-divergent groups.

Young people highlighted a lack of leadership figures in school settings who are trusted on sex related issues and limited in-depth information provision about condom use, risk of STIs and negotiating safe sex.

Theme 3: Interpersonal factors (15 studies)

Male preference regarding condom use in heterosexual relationships often took priority over female preferences.

Communication between partners during sexual activity ranged from uncertainty about how to discuss condom use to deliberate suppression of such discussions, including in coercive situations and cases of stealthing, where a condom is removed without the partner's knowledge.

Condomless sex was more common in long-term relationships, which was sometimes a mutual decision. However, in heterosexual relationships, women's voices are sometimes dismissed by the male partner.

Theme 4: Intrapersonal factors (26 studies)

Embarrassment and shame discouraged some young people from buying condoms or accessing sexual health services, particularly MSM who experienced social judgement, while heterosexual men viewed sexuality more positively, with some associating avoiding condoms as supporting a "masculine" identity.

Young people, including those from ethnic minorities and LGBTQ+ groups, wanted better sexual health information, with engaging advertising and clearer signposting to services. Opportunities to experiment with condoms and associated items such as lubricant were viewed positively for building knowledge and skills.

Attitudes toward condom use were strongly linked to perceived STI risk, although some young people still preferred the risk of infection over reduced sexual pleasure when using condoms.

Impulsivity, the perception that condoms are a "hassle," drug/alcohol use and expectations among some heterosexual men that women should manage pregnancy prevention reduced consistent condom use.

- Factors influencing condom use vary across different groups of young people, meaning different approaches will be needed for different population groups.
- Condom use, or non-use, is heavily influenced by society and gender norms around sexual behaviour, which can disproportionately impact on certain communities including socially excluded young men or those from some ethnic minority communities.

What are the implications of this review?

This systematic review aimed to inform and support decision making around improving condom use in young people. Key implications include:

Policy:

- Develop strategies to support health and care services deliver tailored sexual health care which promotes sex within healthy, consenting relationships.
- Support and empower women, particularly those from some religious/ethnic minority communities, to access education and sexual health services to access the care they need and have their wishes respected within their intimate relationships.
- Acknowledge how sex contributes to young men's developing identity and status among peers, considering how their views of sex/relationships can be changed to support responsibility for their own and their partner's sexual health, and respect of their partners' needs and wishes. Consideration of the impact of societal/community expectations regarding sexual behaviour on men from certain ethnic minority and socially-excluded backgrounds is key.

Health services:

- Provide accessible, culturally sensitive, and youth friendly sexual health support by improving access to free condoms, femidoms and dental dams and guidance and offering engaging, up to date resources.

School education:

- Deliver inclusive, tailored, comprehensive, and relatable sexual health education promoting informed decision making, negotiation of consensual sex/condom use and awareness of support services.

Further research:

- Explore experiences and support needs of all groups within LGBTQ+ communities & regarding managing healthy relationships and sexual health.
- Consider the needs of sex workers in managing their sexual health.
- Develop and evaluate interventions promoting condom use as a typical part of enacting a healthy masculine identity.

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